

Abstract

This paper describes a methodology for the simulation of economic statistics related to a mining mega-project. In particular, the Ring of Fire project in Ontario, Canada. This project has large economic potential based on a combination of public funding for infrastructure used by many new mining operations in a project area of 5,000 square kilometres, which is twice the size of the country of Luxembourg. The paper presents various historical data estimates and shows how to simulate missing data to compare the two estimates. The paper explores what happens if the Canadian military funded the entire project and how military spending on this mega-project could have a 4.0x multiplier on GDP.

Keywords: Natural Resources, Mining, Critical Minerals, Canada, Ontario, Mega Projects, Ring of Fire, Infrastructure, Military

JEL Codes:

B5 - Current Heterodox Approaches
C8 - Data Collection and Data Estimation Methodology Computer Programs
C81 - Methodology for Collecting, Estimating, and Organizing Microeconomic Data; Data Access
E6 - Policy Objectives ; Policy Designs and Consistency ; Policy Coordination
G1 - General Financial Markets
G17 - Financial Forecasting and Simulation
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K2 - Regulation and Business Law
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L5 - Regulation and Industrial Policy
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L72 - Mining, Extraction, and Refining: Other Nonrenewable Resources
N5 - Agriculture, Natural Resources, Environment, and Extractive Industries
O2 - Development Planning and Policy
P11 - Planning, Coordination, and Reform
P16 - Political Economy
Q4 - Energy
Q5 - Environmental Economics
Q32 - Exhaustible Resources and Economic Development
Q33 - Resource Booms
Y1 - Data: Tables and Charts

Method for Estimating GDP Impacts of Mega Mining Projects in Ontario, Canada

This paper describes a methodology for the simulation of economic statistics related to a mining mega-project. In particular, the Ring of Fire project in Ontario, Canada. This project has large economic potential based on a combination of public funding for infrastructure used by many new mining operations in a project area of 5,000 square kilometres, which is twice the size of the country of Luxembourg. The paper presents various historical data estimates and shows how to simulate missing data to compare the two estimates. The paper explores what happens if the Canadian military funded the entire project and how military spending on this mega-project could have a 4.0x multiplier on GDP.

The Ontario Chamber of Commerce (2014) report from ten years ago provides a valuable reference for how the Ring of Fire project has grown over time. The report provides perspectives on possible strategies for the mega-project in terms of new ideas for public-private partnerships that have not yet been tested. Also, the 2014 report provides estimates for economic statistics that can be compared to current estimates for the project, as detailed below.

The Ontario Chamber of Commerce (2014) report highlights that the Ring of Fire project will generate “*up to \$9.4 billion in Gross Domestic Product... and generate nearly \$2 billion in government revenue*” over a ten-year timeline. The 2014 report does not provide annual details, so I use the average across all ten years as the estimate for the annual values of GDP impacts and tax revenues. I compare them to current data from the Ontario Ring of Fire (2025).

Table 1: Estimates for GDP Impacts for Ring Of Fire (CAD \$ billions per year)

Per Year	Total GDP	Direct GDP	Indirect GDP	Total Taxes
2014 Estimate	\$0.6	\$0.9	\$0.3	\$0.2
2025 Estimate	\$4.1	\$3.0	\$1.1	\$2.0
Total Growth	661%	319%	344%	1053%
Annual Growth Rate	19%	11%	12%	24%

There is a substantial increase in the estimated impact of this mega-project over ten years. These are partly due to increases in metal prices, which cause an increase in top-line revenues for all projects. And also due to the fact that costs are increasing, which also increases the total economic activity associated with the project.

The 2014 data (Ontario Chamber of Commerce, 2014) present direct and indirect GDP impacts, but do not include revenues or costs for specific metals production. In contrast, the 2025 data does not include GDP estimates but does include metals production. This mismatch between data availability over time can limit the ability to directly compare different sets of results, but it is possible to simulate missing data. This paper shows how to use the metals production estimates in 2025 to make the GDP estimates as reported in Table 1 using the methods described below.

The 2025 report (Ring of Fire, 2025) includes a breakdown of total metal production for five types of metals: nickel, chromite, copper, and PGMs. The report provides details for total production amounts and prices for each metal. It also provides operating costs and capital costs for nickel; this paper calculates the ratio of costs to metal prices for nickel, and uses similar values to estimate costs for the other metals as follows.

Table 2: Annual Production Tonnage, Prices, and Costs for the Ring of Fire as in 2025

Per Year	Annual Tonnage Metals	Metals Price Per Tonne	OPEX per tonne	CAPEX per tonne	OPEX / Metals Price	CAPEX / Metals Price
Nickel	50,000	\$21,000	\$10,000	\$2,000	48%	10%
Chromite	1,000,000	\$290	\$200	\$40	69%	14%
Copper	20,000	\$10,000	\$5,000	\$1,000	50%	10%
Platinum	5,000	\$30,000	\$15,000	\$3,000	50%	10%

The data in Table 2 shows that the operating margins for each metal are around 50% each year. The ratio of capital costs each year divided by the metals price is around 10%, which is a type of capital intensity to compare capital costs between different metals.

This paper calculates the total amounts for each variable as in the Ontario Ring of Fire (2025) report in Table 3 below. Total revenue is the total metal production multiplied by the metal price, and is also referred to as Gross Metal Value or Primary Mineral Production. The Total Costs are equal to the CAPEX capital costs and OPEX operating costs, as in Table 3.

Table 3: Total Annual Revenue, Costs, and Operating Income by Metals

Per Year	Revenue	Total Costs	CAPEX	OPEX	Operating Income
Nickel	\$1,050,000,000	\$600,000,000	\$100,000,000	\$500,000,000	\$450,000,000
Chromite	\$290,000,000	\$240,000,000	\$40,000,000	\$200,000,000	\$50,000,000
Copper	\$200,000,000	\$120,000,000	\$20,000,000	\$100,000,000	\$80,000,000
Platinum	\$150,000,000	\$90,000,000	\$15,000,000	\$75,000,000	\$60,000,000
Total	\$1,690,000,000	\$1,050,000,000	\$175,000,000	\$875,000,000	\$640,000,000

The lion's share of the mega-project comes from nickel in this model. The Ring of Fire produces ten times as much income from nickel as chromite, although it yields twenty times as much chromite metal as nickel metal. This difference shows that nickel has more revenue and more profit, whereas chromite has a larger tonnage. It is unclear if the mega-project requires the chromite or if it can be redesigned to just focus on the nickel projects. It would be helpful to have a more detailed breakdown of the revenues and costs each year, and whether the amounts can be changed by altering the overall scale of the Ring of Fire project. In addition, there is very high uncertainty over the future values of metal prices and costs.

Natural Resources Canada (2025) provides details on the national economic statistics for total mineral production, direct GDP, and indirect GDP impacts. Mining has an economic multiplier because it represents a new increase in primary production. The ratio is equal to 1.75x for direct GDP relative to total mineral value. The ratio increases to 2.4x for the total GDP impact relative to total mineral value in Canada. The difference is due to indirect impacts. These ratios can be used to estimate the GDP impact of the mining activity reported in Table 3.

Table 4: GDP Impacts of Mining in the Ring of Fire Mega-Project

Per Year	Total Mineral Value	Direct GDP (1.75x)	Total GDP (2.4x)
Nickel	\$1,050,000,000	\$1,837,500,000	\$2,520,000,000
Chromite	\$290,000,000	\$507,500,000	\$696,000,000
Copper	\$200,000,000	\$350,000,000	\$480,000,000
Platinum	\$150,000,000	\$262,500,000	\$360,000,000
Total	\$1,690,000,000	\$2,957,500,000	\$4,056,000,000

The total value of new mineral production from the Ring of Fire is approximately \$1.7 billion per year. This new metals production has a direct GDP impact of \$3 billion and another \$1 billion in indirect impacts. The total GDP impact is \$4 billion per year from the Ring of Fire, as in Table 4.

It is possible to compare various national economic statistics to the Ring of Fire mega-project. For example, there is approximately \$40 billion of total metal production per year across Canada. The Ring of Fire would produce approximately \$1.7 billion, which is almost a 5% increase in national metal production. Beyond metals, there is a broader category of minerals as defined by Natural Resources Canada (2025): *“In 2024, mineral production totalled \$64 billion. Canada produces 60 minerals and metals at 200 mines and thousands of sand and gravel pits and stone quarries.”* Compared with the overall Canadian GDP from all minerals, the Ring of Fire causes an increase of almost 3% as in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Comparing GDP Impacts of Ring of Fire and All Canadian Mining

Per Year	Value of Metals	Direct GDP	Indirect GDP	Total GDP
Ring Of Fire	\$1.7	\$3.0	\$1.1	\$4.1
Canada	\$38.0	\$112.0	\$44.0	\$156.0
Ring of Fire as % of Canada	4.5%	2.7%	2.5%	2.6%

The Ring of Fire is a substantial project, and the annual costs are around \$1 billion. The Government of Canada is committed to investing in this project, but what if it owned it outright? For example, what if the Canadian military were responsible for funding all of the Ring of Fire mega-project? If the Canadian military funded and executed a mega-project like the Ring of Fire, then how would it impact the security of supply for critical minerals like nickel or copper? How would it impact global metals supply chains?

If the Canadian military paid for all the costs of the Ring of Fire mega-project, then it would cost \$1 billion and generate \$4 billion in new GDP per year. This provides a 4x multiplier for military spending on this mega-project. The \$1 billion in costs would represent a new type of military spending. In contrast, the \$4 billion in new GDP includes the total value of all metal production and all direct and indirect impacts. It is unrealistic to assume the military could own all of the mega-projects itself because the projects are owned privately now. However, it is helpful to identify the potential GDP multiplier of military spending on domestic primary production. It may be possible to analyze specifically what parts of the total capital costs for the Ring of Fire mega projects could be built by the Canadian military, but that is beyond the scope of this article.

Total military spending in Canada was approximately \$40 billion CAD in 2024, and it must increase by \$20 billion CAD to meet NATO targets since total GDP was around \$2.9 trillion CAD (Government of Canada, 2025). The definition of “military spending” for the NATO targets is broad and can include domestic infrastructure and heavy industry, like the Ring of Fire mega-projects. It would require approximately 5% of the total new military spending to fund the entire Ring of Fire mega-project. In addition, the military might actually earn \$1.7 billion in revenue from the project from metals production. The Canadian military is not in the mining business, but maybe it should be!

References

Government of Canada, (2025), “*Addendum: National Defence Funding and Projected Canadian Defence Spending to GDP*,” *Our North, Strong and Free: A Renewed Vision for Canada’s Defence*.

<https://www.canada.ca/en/department-national-defence/corporate/reports-publications/north-strong-free-2024/addendum-national-defence-funding-and-projected-canadian-defence-spending-to-gdp.html>

Natural Resources Canada, (2025), “10 Key Facts on Canada’s Mineral Sector,” Accessed November 21, 2025:

https://natural-resources.canada.ca/sites/admin/files/documents/2025-08/10_key_facts_mineral_sector_July2025_e.pdf

Ontario Chamber of Commerce, (2014), “BENEATH the SURFACE Uncovering the Economic Potential of Ontario’s Ring of Fire”

https://occ.ca/wp-content/uploads/Beneath_the_Surface_web-1.pdf

Ontario Ring of Fire, (2025), “Economic Data”

<https://www.orof.ca/ring-of-fire-map/economic-data/#simple-content-2>